

The Influence of Storytelling Apron Media on the Speaking Skills of Children Aged 5-6 Years at TK Karunia, Medan Johor District, Academic Year 2022/2023

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the effect of storytelling media on the speaking skills of children aged 5-6 years. This study uses an approach with an experimental method (Quasi-Experimental Design) in the form of The Equivalent Time Samples Design. The population in this study were all children aged 5-6 years at kindergarten Karunia for the 2023/2024 academic year. From the data the results of data analysis have an average score of treatment 1 of 2.5, treatment 2 gets an average value of 6.1 while treatment 3 gets an average value of 9.3. Based on data analysis through non-parametric hypothesis testing, the SPSS 25 statistical test value is 0.005. There is a significant influence between the use of storytelling media on the speaking skills of children aged 5-6 years at TK Karunia, Medan Johor District, Academic Year 2022/2023.

INTRODUCTION

Based on Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, Article 1 point 14 states that Early Childhood Education (PAUD) is education provided to children from birth to the age of six, which is carried out through providing education that supports growth and development. physically and intellectually so that children are ready to participate in further education (Lestarinigrum, 2017).

In early childhood language learning there are four aspects of skill development, namely, listening skills, reading skills, writing skills and speaking skills. Speaking skills are one of the basic skills that are important to develop in children from an early age, because speaking skills are the skills that children use most often and apply in everyday life. By having good speaking skills, children can express their thoughts, ideas and feelings through spoken language to other people. Furthermore, Tarigan (Khasanah, 2022) explains that speaking skills are the ability to pronounce sounds or words to express and express thoughts, ideas and feelings.

Furthermore, Tadjuddin (2015) stated that children's speech development when they reach the age of 4-6 years is such that children know how to use words in a more complex way. Example: "Mom, I prefer the red dress, the green one is not good." In line with this, the speaking ability of children aged 5-6 years is, saying sentences with six to eight words, being able to explain the meaning of simple words, knowing opposite words, using conjunctions, prepositions and articles, saying simple words and speaking fluently. , easy to understand and follows grammar even though there are still errors in language (Elfiah Rifda, 2019).

The utilization of learning media by teachers is also a factor that can influence children's speaking skills. By using learning media, the teaching and learning process will be more fun and attract children's attention to be more enthusiastic about learning. One of them is the use of story-telling apron learning media. In line with this, Dhieni (Madyawati, 2020) revealed that playing with a storytelling apron is considered suitable for use in language activities to improve children's speaking skills.

As an educator, you are required to be skilled and creative in using learning media that can stimulate the skills of early childhood. Just like speaking skills, with skilled speaking children will easily communicate and convey the various ideas they have. One of the media that can be used to develop children's speaking skills is the storytelling apron media.

Considering the findings of preliminary survey that took place when implementing PLP 2 at TK Karunia, Medan Johor District and running for approximately 30 days, shows that the child's speaking skills have begun to develop but are not yet optimal and need to be given more stimulation. Of all the children in group B, TK Karunia, Medan Johor District as many as 20 children, when asked questions by the teacher, 5 children were able to answer the questions, but 15 children were not correct in answering the teacher's questions. There are still children who remain silent when invited by the teacher to give an opinion about something. Several factors cause the

speaking skills of children aged 5-6 years at TK Karunia to not develop optimally namely because the learning strategies used by teachers do not make much use of media, especially in learning children's speaking skills.

Based on the problems above, researchers have a solution to solve problems in the speaking skills of children aged 5-6 years through the medium of storytelling aprons. Storytelling aprons are a form of learning media in the form of cloth with pictures that you make yourself and use flannel cloth by combining several colors and attaching interesting pictures according to the story you want to tell. (Madyawati, 2020) explains that a storytelling apron is a physical device in the form of a cloth covering a shirt attached to the chest which is used to help convey messages, information or fairy tales that are listened to in a fun way. In line with that, Nata in (Madyawati, 2020) explains that the activity of telling stories with a story apron has been modified into an educational prop to convey the content of the story."

Several studies relevant to this research were carried out by (Juariyah, 2017) when using storytelling aprons on children's listening skills, the results of the research concluded that these storytelling aprons had an effect on listening skills. Then research carried out by (Putri & Jati, 2019) when using the story method with a flannel apron on beginning reading ability, the results of the research concluded that there was a significant influence between the story method assisted by a flannel apron on children's beginning reading ability.

Researchers want to use media that will hopefully attract children's attention and stimulate their speaking skills. This storytelling apron media will be packaged with stories that encourage children to be skilled in speaking. Children will be invited to listen to stories told by the teacher. After the storytelling activity is carried out, the teacher will give the children the opportunity to retell the story simply and ask questions related to the story that was told. Then it ends with the teacher and children together concluding the moral message content of the storytelling activity.

Based on the background above, the author was tempted to raise the research title "The Influence of Storytelling Apron Media on the Speaking Skills of Children Aged 5-6 Years in TK Karunia, Medan Johor District Academic Year 2022/2023".

LITERATURE REVIEW

The influence of story-telling apron media on the speaking skills of children aged 5-6 years
Speaking Skills of Children Aged 5-6 Years

Speaking is a basic skill that every child must master before they can speak well. This is reasonable because through speaking each individual can convey what they want. According to Aguilar (Khasanah, 2022) states "speaking is an interactive building process, meaning it involves the production and reception and processing of information. How do children process words into sentences so that what is meant can be understood by other

people who are invited to interact? In speaking activities you should also pay attention to what factors influence speaking skills.

In line with this, Agung (Karmilla & Purwadi, 2019), there are two factors that influence speaking skills, namely:

1. Internal factors, are all the potential that exists within a person.

Internal factors include:

- a. Physical factors are factors related to the perfection of the body organs used in speaking, in this case including the vocal cords, tongue, teeth and lips.
- b. Non-physical (psychic) factors are factors that are related to a person's psychological condition and are not related to the physical. Psychological factors of speaking skills include:
 - Personality (charisma), the personality that one has influences the way a person speaks.
 - Character and temperament, Character is the result of the way of thinking and behaving. Character starts from a mindset which is then manifested in actions, which if done continuously will become a habit.
 - Talent (talent), Talent is a gift from God given to someone. Talent needs to be explored until it comes to the surface (because basically talent is something that has existed before).
 - Intelligence level, skills to act purposefully, think rationally, and deal with the environment effectively.
 - Creativity, Creativity has almost the same position as intelligence. Creativity is one of the characteristics of intelligent thinking, because both are manifestations of cognitive thinking

2. External factors

External factors are factors that originate from outside the individual which include education level, habits and social environment. Hurlock (Karmilla & Purwadi, 2019, p. 133) stated that there are two criteria that can be used to decide whether a child is speaking in the correct sense or just "parroting". First, children must know the meaning of the words they use and associate them with the objects they represent. Second, the child must pronounce the words so that others understand them easily. Words that children can only understand because they have heard them often or because they have learned to understand them and suspect what is being said do not meet these criteria.

Storytelling Apron Media

Moeslichatun (Madyawati, 2020) states that a storytelling apron is a physical means in the form of a cloth covering a shirt attached to the

chest which is used to help convey messages, information or fairy tales that are listened to in a fun way.

In line with the opinion above, Nata (Madyawati, 2020) stated that the method of telling stories using a story apron is an activity of conveying story content using an apron that has been modified into an educational prop. It is hoped that the use of storytelling apron media can help attract children's attention to the stories told by the teacher.

According to Susilawati's opinion (Madyawati, 2020), she expressed the benefits of telling stories with a story apron, namely being a basic foundation for verbal abilities, improving listening skills, sharpening logical thinking and curiosity, increasing insight, developing children's imagination, increasing emotional intelligence, and a tool to improve moral values, ethics, and personal development.

The previous research that supports this research is Betti Juariyah & Maubah (2017), The research results concluded that the storytelling apron had an effect on listening skills. Apart from that, Nelva Mulia Novianti Putri, et al (2019), Derta & Padilah (2022) concluded that there is a significant influence between the storytelling method assisted by a flannel apron on children's early reading abilities. Monica Hotma Elya (2020), concluded that there is an interaction effect between storytelling methods and learning styles on children's speaking abilities. This means that to improve children's speaking skills, the application of the storytelling method must be adapted to the child's learning style. Children with an auditory learning style who are taught using the storytelling method with hand puppets have higher speaking abilities than children who are taught.

Ha: There is a significant influence from the use of storytelling aprons on the speaking skills of children aged 5-6 years at TK Karunia, Medan Johor District, Academic Year 2022/2023

METHODOLOGY

The type of research used in this research is experimental research. The design in this research is a Quasi Experiment Design with the design form The Equivalent Time Sample Design.

The location of this research was carried out at TK Karunia which is located on Jalan Eka Rasmi No. 36, Johor Building, District. Medan Johor, Medan City, North Sumatra. The time for carrying out this research is in the even semester of the 2022/2023 academic year from February to June 2023.

The population in this study was all children aged 5-6 years at TK Karunia for the 2023/2024 academic year. Which consists of two classes, namely class B-1 consisting of 10 children and class B-2 consisting of 10 children, so the total number is 20 children.

The instrument used to obtain data is a non-test instrument in the form of an observation sheet containing indicators and descriptors regarding the speaking skills of children aged 5-6 years. The data collection technique in this research uses non-test instruments, namely observation of children's

speaking abilities. With a score of 1 = if only 1 descriptor appears, score 2 = if only 2 descriptors appear, score 3 = if 3 descriptors appear.

The procedural techniques in this research start from the preparation stage, implementation stage and final stage and the research design starts from the preparation, implementation and evaluation stages.

The analysis technique used in this research is nonparametric data analysis techniques. In this research, a non-parametric test was used, namely the Wilcoxon Test, to test whether the hypothesis is acceptable or not. Testing was carried out using a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. If the smallest absolute score is less than or equal to the critical value score determined in the Wilcoxon Test, the null hypothesis (H0) is accepted and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) is rejected. The stages of data analysis techniques for carrying out this research include: categorizing children's speaking skills data and inputting the calculation results into the categorization.

RESEARCH RESULTS

In this research hypothesis testing was carried out through the use of non-parametric statistics. In testing the truth of the hypothesis, non-parametric tests, especially the Wilcoxon Test, are used. In this research, a real level of $\alpha = 0.05$ was used.

Observations 1 and 2

Ranks

N		n	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Observation 2	Negative Ranks	0a	.00	.00
Observation 1	Positive Ranks	10b	5.50	55.00
	Ties	0c		
	Total	10		

Table 1. Ranks of Observations 1 and 2

- a. Observation 2 < Observation 1
- b. Observation 2 > Observation 1
- c. Observation 2 = Observation 1

Based on the table above, the ranking interpretation is as follows:

- a. Negative ranks or the difference (negative) between the results of observations 1 and 2 is 0, both in the N value, Mean Rank, and Sum Ranks. A value of 0 indicates there is no decrease or reduction from the value of observation 1 to observation 2.
- b. Positive ranks or the positive difference between the results of

observation 1 and observation 2. Here there are 10 positive data (N) which means that the 10 students experienced an increase in the results from observation value 1 to observation value 2. The mean rank or average increase is equal to 5.50. Meanwhile, the number of positive ranks or sum of ranks is 55.00.

- c. Ties is the security value of Observation 1 and Observation 2, here the tie value is 0, so it can be said that there is no equal value between observation 1 and observation 2.

Test Statistics

		Observation2 - Observation 1
Z		-2.972b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	Sig. (2-tailed)	,003

- a. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test
- b. Based on negative ranks.

Table 2. Test Statistics for Observations 1 and 2

Based on the output of "test statistics", it is known that Asymp. Sig. (2- tailed) has a value of 0.003 which is smaller than <0.05, so it can be concluded that the "hypothesis is accepted" meaning there is a difference in the value results for observation 1 and observation 2, so it can also be concluded that "there is an influence of the use of storytelling aprons on speaking skills children aged 5-6 years at TK Karunia Medan Johor District class B".

Observations 3 and 4
Ranks

N			Mean Rank	Sum Rank
Observation 4 - Observation 3	4	Negative Ranks	0a	.00
		Positive Ranks	10b	55.00
		Ties	0c	
		Total	10	

- a. Observation 4 < Observation 3
- b. Observation 4 > Observation 3
- c. Observation 4 = Observation 3

- Based on the table above, the ranking interpretation is as follows:
- Negative ranks or the difference (negative) between observation results 3 and 4 is 0, both in the N value, Mean Rank, and Sum Ranks. A value of 0 indicates there is no decrease or reduction from the value of observation 3 to observation 4.
 - Positive ranks or the positive difference between the results of observation 3 and observation 4. Here there are 10 positive data (N), which means that the 10 students experienced an increase in the results from observation value 3 to observation value 4. The mean rank or average increase is equal to 5.50. Meanwhile, the number of positive ranks or sum of ranks is 55.00.
 - Ties is the security value of Observation 3 and Observation 4, here the tie value is 0, so it can be said that there is no equal value between observation 3 and observation 4.

Test Statistics

		Observation 4 - Observation 3
Z		-2.871b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,004

- Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test
- Based on negative ranks.

Based on the output of "test statistics", it is known that Asymp. Sig. (2- tailed) has a value of 0.004 which is smaller than <0.05, so it can be concluded that the "hypothesis is accepted" meaning there is a difference in the value results for observation 3 and observation 4, so it can also be concluded that "there is an influence of the use of storytelling aprons on speaking skills children aged 5-6 years at TK Karunia Medan Johor District class B".

Observations 5 and 6

N			Mean Rank	Sum Ranks
Observation 5	Negative Ranks	0a	.00	.00
	Positive Ranks	10b	5.50	55.00
	Ties	0c		
	Total	10		

Table 5. Ranks of Observations 5 and 6

- a. Observation 6 < Observation 5
- b. Observation 6 > Observation 5
- c. Observation 6 = Observation 5

Based on the table above, the ranking interpretation is as follows:

- a. Negative ranks or the difference (negative) between observation results 5 and 6 is 0, both in the N value, Mean Rank, and Sum Ranks. A value of 0 indicates there is no decrease or reduction from observation value 5 to observation 6.
- b. Positive ranks or the positive difference between the results of observation 5 and observation 6. Here there are 10 positive data (N), which means that the 10 students experienced an increase in the results from observation value 5 to observation value 6. The mean rank or average increase is equal to 5.50. Meanwhile, the number of positive ranks or sum of ranks is 55.00.
- c. Ties is the security value of Observation 5 and Observation 6, here the tie value is 0, so it can be said that there is no equal value between observation 5 and observation 6.

Test Statistics

		Observation 6 - Observation 5
Z		-2.831b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,005

- a. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test
- b. Based on negative ranks.

Based on the output of "test statistics", it is known that Asymp. Sig. (2- tailed) has a value of 0.005 which is smaller than <0.05, so it can be concluded that "the hypothesis is accepted" meaning there is a difference in the value results for observation 5 and observation 6, so it can also be concluded that "there is an influence of the use of storytelling aprons on speaking skills children aged 5-6 years at TK Karunia Medan Johor District class B".

According to Elfiah Rifda (2019), the speaking ability of children aged 5-6 years is able to pronounce sentences with 6-8 words. However, in reality, the results of the research prove that the speaking skills of children aged 5-6 years at TK Karunia, Medan Johor District, class B in treatment 1 child still said sentences with 3 words, for example the child said the simple sentence "Fish swim in the water", then in treatment 2 children still saying sentences with 5 words, for example the child said the simple sentence "The kitten went away from home" and in treatment 3 showed improvement where the child was able to say 8 words. For example,

children say simple sentences through stories, such as "The rabbit lost the running race because the rabbit slept under the tree."

DISCUSSION

In accordance with the information investigation that has been completed, it can be proven that there is a significant influence from the use of story-telling aprons on the speaking skills of children aged 5-6 years at TK Karunia, Medan Johor District for the 2022/2023 academic year, this is shown from the SPSS 25 statistical test obtained The real level $\alpha (0.05) < 0.05$ so the speculation expresses that there is a huge impact. This is because stories using storytelling aprons are presented to attract more attention so that children can practice their ability to speak, respond to what they see, answer things that are asked and retell in their own language the stories they hear.

The results of this research are in line with Nata's opinion (Madyawati, 2020) which states that the method of telling stories using a story apron is an activity of conveying story content using an apron that has been modified into an educational prop. It is hoped that the use of storytelling apron media can help attract children's attention to the stories told by the teacher. Apart from that, Windy (Madyawati, 2020) believes that the advantage of story activities with storytelling aprons is that they stimulate children's thinking and imagination. Children can express various ideas according to the pictures they see. Creating a pleasant atmosphere that will speed up the child's learning process. Develop language skills, especially the ability to express language and train children to communicate verbally."

In this study, there were 3 treatments, which means 3 times carrying out storytelling activities with a storytelling apron. Treatment 1 tells the story of the rabbit and the turtle which contains the moral value of not looking down on other people or feeling arrogant about the skills we have. Treatment 2 tells the story of a goldfish who never gives up which contains the moral value of having a great sense of enthusiasm and not giving up easily in solving the problems encountered. Then treatment 3 tells the story of a mother cat and her kittens which contains the moral of obeying, loving and helping parents.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Depended on the findings of the study and discussions that has been portrayed, it very well may be inferred that:

1. Based on the results of the research and discussion explained above, there is a significant influence between the use of storytelling aprons on the speaking skills of children aged 5-6 years at TK Karunia, Medan Johor District, Academic Year 2022/2023. This can be seen from the results in treatment 1, there were (8) children in the low category with a percentage value of 80%. In treatment 2 there were (7) children in the medium category with a percentage score of 70%. And in treatment 3 there was a

significant increase, where (6) children had entered the high category with a percentage of 60%.

2. Telling stories using an apron is presented to attract more attention so that children can practice their ability to speak, respond to what they see, answer questions asked and tell stories from everything they see. And it has a very important impact on children. Because it doesn't just entertain children but can also educate children through good stories, it will stimulate children's understanding of things and the development of children to provide opinions or ideas that they have.

Recommendations

From the research results and conclusions that have been presented, several recommendations as follows:

1. Kindergarten/PAUD teachers are expected to be able to use storytelling aprons as a tool in the learning process.
2. School principals should be able to work together in providing the tools and materials needed for the learning process and always monitor the availability of media or tools needed for the learning process.

For future researchers who want to do further research, they can add to the discussion of qualitative data from the research results to strengthen the analysis and add different variables.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

For advanced research, we hope to be able to see or analyze better the data related to the influence of Storytelling Apron Media on the Speaking Skills of Children Aged 5-6 Years.

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REFERENCES

- Elya, M. H., Nadiroh, N., & Nurani, Y. (2019). Pengaruh metode bercerita dan gaya belajar terhadap kemampuan berbicara anak usia dini. *Jurnal Obsesi: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, 4(1), 302-315.
- Elfiah, Rifda. 2019. *Bimbingan Dan Konseling Anak Usia Dini*. Depok. PT Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Juariyah, B. (2017). Pengaruh Media Celemek Cerita Terhadap Keterampilan Menyimak Anak Usia 4-5 Tahun Di TK Aisyiyah Bustanul Athfal Cabang Loceret Nganjuk. *Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini Teratai*.

- Khasanah, Uswatun, Mohammad Atwi Suparman dan Basuki Wibawa. 2022. Model Pembelajaran Keterampilan Berbicara Anak Usia Dini Menggunakan Big Book. Jakarta. Kencana.
- Lestarinigrum, Anik. 2017. Perencanaan Pembelajaran Anak Usia Dini.
- Watudandang Prambon Nganjuk. Adjie Media Nusantara Nganjuk Madyawati, Lilis. 2020. Strategi Pengembangan Bahasa Pada Anak. Jakarta. Kencana.
- Mursid, 2017. Pengembangan Pembelajaran PAUD. Bandung. PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Nur, Indah Manfaati. 2020. Metode Statistik Non Parametrik dan Aplikasinya pada Bidang Kesehatan. Semarang.
- Nuriza, S. L. Pengaruh Penggunaan Media Celemek Bercerita Terhadap Kemampuan Menceritakan Kembali Teks Fabel Siswa VII SMPN 3 Mojoagung.
- Putri, N. M. N., & Jati, S. N. (2019). Efektivitas Metode Bercerita Berbantu Kain Celemek Flanel Terhadap Kemampuan Membaca Permulaan Pada Anak Kelompok B Di PAUD Gitananda. *Edukasi: Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, 6(2).
- Susanto, Ahmad. 2011. Perkembangan Anak Usia Dini: Pengantar Dalam Berbagai Aspeknya. Jakarta. Kencana.
- Sugiyono. 2021. Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif Dan R&D. Bandung. Alfabeta
- Sulistiyawati, R., & Amelia, Z. (2021). Meningkatkan Kemampuan Berbicara Anak Melalui Media Big Book. *Jurnal Anak Usia Dini Holistik Integratif (AUDHI)*, 2(2), 67-78.
- Tadjuddin, Nilawati. 2015. Desain Pembelajaran Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini. Bandar Lampung. Aura Printing & Publishing.
- Trimansyah, Bambang. 2020. Panduan Penulisan Buku Cerita Anak. Cimahi. Pusat Pembinaan Bahasa dan Sastra.
- Yusuf, A. M. (2017). Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif & Penelitian Gabungan. Jakarta: Kencana.